

Overseas Shinto Shrines

also known as “Shinto Shrines outside of Japan”

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Entry tags: Sacred mountain, Religious Group, Japanese, Secularism, Japanese Religions, Shrine, Korean Religions, Shrines, Shintō, Military Cults, Japan-Taiwan Japanese, Sacred Land, Language, Religious Place, Japonic, Kami worship, Taiwan, Japan, Korea, Sakhalin, Micronesia, Hawaii, Japanese, Chinese Religion

Overseas Shinto Shrines, or kaigai jinja, are shrines located outside of the current borders of Japan. This includes official recognized shrines in Japanese colonies such as Karafuto (Sakhalin), Taiwan, Korea, and the Kwangtung Leased area. It also includes shrines within the wider sphere of Japanese influence, including the Asian continent (Manchukuo, China, South East Asia), the South Pacific (Micronesia, Hawaii) and to a lesser extent the American continents (U.S. mainland and Brazil). Although not yet common, newly established overseas Shinto shrines can also be found in Europe.

Date Range: 1868 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Japanese Sphere of Influence in early 1940s

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, East Asia, China, Democratic People's Republic of Korea, Japan, Mongolia, Republic of Korea, Oceania, Micronesia, Hawaii, Global, United States, Taiwan, Southeast Asia, Japan, Hawaii, East Asia, Taiwan

The sphere of influence imperial Japan claimed in the early 1940s, esp. in relation to encouraging the construction of shrines

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Nakajima Michio. 2010. "Shinto Deities that Crossed the Sea: Japan's 'Overseas Shrines', 1968-1945". *Japanese Journal of Religious Studies* 37/1:21-46
- Source 2: Zushi Minoru. 2003. *Shinyaku Jinja: Yasukuni Shisou wo kangaeru Tame ni*. Tokyo: Shinkansha.
- Source 3: Shimizu, Karli. 2023. *Overseas Shinto Shrines: Religion, Secularity and the Japanese Empire*. London: Bloomsbury Academic.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.himoji.jp/database/db04/>

– Source 1 Description: Kanagawa University's Database of Overseas Shinto Shrines

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2003-2006

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Kanagawa University's Database of Overseas Shinto Shrines did surveys of remaining overseas shrine sites.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Tree, grove, or forest

– Other [specify]: Mountain

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Clearing

– Water feature

– Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: Often located at the edge of a city or town, but not always.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

Notes: At unofficial shrines, there may be only a clearing without a building. But official shrines

must have structures.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes. As finances allow, shrines have often expanded in multiples stages of construction.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes. As finances allow, extra features during multiple stages of construction may be added to make the shrine grander.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: Veneration

– Social

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For political reasons

– As the result of war

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Notes: In some cases, shrines might be destroyed by natural phenomena and remain as ruins. However, the ideal would be to rebuild them.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: In some cases, postwar shrines have been reconstructed on a smaller scale.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: They are for venerating kami. During the period when overseas shrines were rapidly expanding, kami were not considered supernatural by the government, but considered heroic or patriotic historical figures. Receiving oracles from kami ("communication with kami") was also considered superstitious and not suitable for shrines during this period.

– Yes

Notes: Although the official government understanding of kami was not as a "god" or "supernatural being", postwar kami are generally understood as supernatural by people, esp. overseas.

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Kami

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Kami

Notes: Kami can be singular or plural, but most shrines were dedicated to more than one.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

Notes: Some shrines, esp. gokoku shrines, functioned as cenotaphs.

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Notes: Overseas shrines were public sites and not generally restricted to an ethnic group.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Body present:

– No

↳ Part of body present:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Notes: But overseas shrines sometimes venerated the founder of the nation, such as Amaterasu. As the nation was imagined as a family, you could argue that shrines sometimes commemorated the ethnic group on the whole.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Other [specify]: Shrines were often commissioned by the local or central government.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

- Captured enemies
- Children
- Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: Although specialists were required for many parts of the shrine, volunteer labor from the common populace often played a part constructing the shrine grounds. Schoolchildren groups were often required to volunteer their labor in both construction and maintenance of their nearby shrine. In the mid 1940s, POW were asked/required to work on building shrines, such as at Shonan Jinja.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Notes: There were shrines built at the birthplace of some kami/historical figures, but I would not say that this was typical.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Notes: Shrine construction was usually funded by a combination of government funding (taxes) and donation solicited from the local people. This included donations from Buddhist and new religion groups.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: Overseas shrines were built for various reasons. The government established large shrines both in order to gain the kami's help in developing the land as well as to instill patriotism in the local population.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: However, there were small shrine-like structures called hoan-den built at schools to house the Imperial Rescript on Education. In some cases, these buildings were called shrines by the colonized population.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The front approach of the shrine often had a bridge (shin-bashi) that arched over a river or stream in the shrine's garden.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The haiden (veneration hall) and honden (sanctuary) of the shrine were often connected together with a heiden (a wide hallway or intermediate ritual space).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The most important building is the honden. Shrines often have subsidiary shrines in the garden, which as the name implies are subsidiary to the main shrine.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Notes: But larger shrines sometimes prided themselves on the massive size of their torii gates.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes
– No

Notes: Taiwanese (old-growth) hinoki cypress was commonly used at shrines across the empire due to its quality. And distant places may donate materials to major shrines. But practically, most shrines used local materials, and local sites were more likely to donate materials to nearby shrines.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

Notes: Esp. granite.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes
Notes: Not always, but granite is heavy.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Copper

Notes: Roofs were often done in copper.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Ferroconcrete

Notes: Ferroconcrete was a new technology when overseas shrines were rapidly expanding. It was popular for its affordability, durability, and resistance to termites. It could imitate the look of stone/plaster as well.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– No

Notes: Elements are architecture which used to be functional (such as chigi) and have now become what might be called decorative aspects of shrine architecture. However, the stereotypical shrine architecture is characterized more by lack of decoration than decoration.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Shrine buildings are not usually highly decorated, but votive paintings, shimenawa (straw ropes), and photographs etc. might be displayed by being attached to the building.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Are there humans depicted:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there animals depicted:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
 - No
- ↳ Floral motifs
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: N/A
- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
 - No
- ↳ Are there statues present:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cult statues:
 - No

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: It is not typical to have statues of the kami, but there are exceptions. Furthermore, if there is a statue of the kami, it is not necessarily of them as a "god", but rather them as a historical figure.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Animals

Notes: There are usually statues of komainu (Korean dogs or Chinese lions) flanking the main approach. There may also be statues of other animals such as bronze horses in the Western style or sacred animals such as cows or foxes depending on the shrine.

–Other [specify]: Lanterns

–Other [specify]: Monuments

Notes: Monuments such as obelisks (war memorials) and stone memorials marking other events are common at shrines.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– No

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

Notes: Votive paintings (ema) may include the kami, but not typically.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Horses

Notes: Ema (votive paintings) frequently feature horses as they originated as substitute offerings for real horses.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Donor lists and inscriptions noting the occurrence of an important occasion such as an imperial visit are common.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Landscape Features

Notes: Shrines aimed to have a forested garden with a curved main approach that crossed over a river with a sacred bridge (shinbashi).

–Yes [specify]: Trees

Notes: Particularly old or significant trees were marked with shimenawa ropes at shrines. Trees were also brought from local areas to forest the shrine garden. Furthermore, trees from distant places were donated to the shrine to be planted. Dignitaries such as imperial family members handplanted trees at shrines as memorials of their visit, and these trees were marked with monuments noting this.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: There are rare exceptions such as the Nokotsu Jinja (ossuary shrine) in Manchuria and the graveyard at Hakodate Gokoku Jinja in Hokkaido (sometimes considered overseas). But typically a line was drawn between shrines and gravesites, including cases when the gravesite had a torii gate at it.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: Some overseas shrine, especially gokoku shrines, venerated the eirei (glorious spirits, or the patriotic dead). Furthermore, the kami at most shrines during the colonial period were considered historical figures by the Japanese government.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the kami venerated at overseas shrines were historical persons. During the colonial period, the Japanese government did not consider them "deified", but they have sometimes been considered that way postwar.

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Notes: Kami were often historical persons who were deemed awe-some (heroic), such as Prince Yoshihisa Kitashirakawa, who was widely venerated at shrines in Taiwan, or the patriotic dead (eirei). Furthermore, the Japanese imperial government argued that the ancient kami (e.i. Amaterasu, Emperor Jinmu, Empress Jingu, etc.) were historical heroes, although today these

kami are usually considered mythical "gods".

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: But shrines may have a treasure house with historical objects related to or once belonging to the enshrined kami.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: Prewar, the official stance of the government was that there were no spirits (rei) at shrines. However, this view was not always shared by the populace.

Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors might have a norito ("prayer") read on their behalf addressed to the kami.

Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: It depends on the size of the shrine. An example of a larger shrine is Taiwan Jinja, which had 65 thousand people visit during its main festival in 1901.

Notes: See reference, p.73.

Reference: Taiwan Jinja Shamosho Hensan, ed.. Taiwan Jinja Shi. Edited by Taiwan Jinja Shamosho Hensan. Taipei: Taiwan Nichinichi Shinpousha, 1916.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Daily

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: Alternatives forms of ritual behavior such as Chinese/Confucian style bows approved of by the government, but many Japanese observers criticized colonial subjects for perceived lack of reverence at shrines.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Esp. timed yohai (veneration from afar) practices synchronized citizens across the Japanese empire and beyond.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Omiki (alcohol) is drunk after the main ritual.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Dignitaries might offer jewels or swords for the shrine to keep or display in its treasure house.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Foodstuff such as rice and vegetables is perhaps the most common non-monetary offering at shrines.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Money

–Other [specify]: Labor

Notes: The donation of labor was important for improving the shrine grounds and maintaining the shrine.

–Other [specify]: Trees

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: There is no religious obligation to attend the shrine. However, school children and officials were often required to visit shrines as a demonstration of their patriotism during the first half of the 1900s.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

Notes: It is not required from a religious standpoint, but school children were obligated by their school to donate their time/labor in helping to maintain their local shrine during the prewar/wartime period.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Notes: When donating labor to the shrine, volunteer troupes often underwent purification before starting their work.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: Overseas shrines did not conduct shikinen sengu (periodic rebuilding) like some major shrines (esp. Ise and Izumo) in the Japanese Home Islands. This may be due to their relatively short history. However, they did undergo periodic expansions--which often involved building a bigger main shrine building--to commemorate important events such as the 2600th anniversary of the Japanese empire.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: Permanent shrine ritualists conducted daily maintenance at the shrine.

– No

Notes: Major shrine maintenance was conducted by volunteer groups, or professional companies hired by the shrine.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– Yes

↳ Transition to adulthood

– Yes

Notes: This included coming of age type rituals such as Shichigosan, as well as school entrance and graduation ceremonies.

↳ Death

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Immigrating

Notes: Migrants moving from the Japanese Home Islands to the colonies or farther overseas (Manchukuo, Hawaii, etc.) would often visit the Ise Jingu to receive a talisman to enshrine in their new hometown overseas. Likewise, migrants might announce to the kami of their local shrine their travel plans and pray for safety.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The standard ritual includes partaking in omiki (alcohol) afterwards, while major rituals would include a full naorai meal afterwards.

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– Yes

Notes: The omiki/naorai (alcohol/meal) is often drawn from donations to the shrine, so are indirectly sponsored by local elites and others who have donated to the shrine.

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

Notes: The omiki/naorai (alcohol/meal) is often drawn from donations to the shrine, so are indirectly sponsored by local elites and others who have donated to the shrine.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Government

Notes: Until 1945, shrines were public sites funded in part by the government.

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Large shrines had a specialized event hall built within the shrine grounds. Smaller shrines use the oratory (haiden) for feasting.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Everyday

Notes: Ritualists conduct a daily "festival" everyday, while a regular monthly festival (tsukinami-sai) is held once or twice a month.

– specify: Approx. Monthly

Notes: Each shrine has a calendar of more major festivals, with festivals occurring about once a month on average.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

– Elites

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Shrines for all members of society to attend larger festivals. Smaller festivals are attended only by elites and/or ritualists. In some cases, esp. in Manchukuo, Japanese Home Islanders excluded non ethnic-Japanese from visiting the shrine, despite this being against official government policy.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– No

Notes: As festivals (matsuri) are conducted every day, regular cleaning is standard at shrines. But preparation for major festivals might include extra cleaning or replacement of worn-out goods etc.

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: It depends upon the size of the shrine and the importance of the festival.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Notes: Divination practices may have occurred at some shrines (ex: Hawaii Daijingu in early 1900s), but this was criticized by the broader shrine establishment.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Smaller shrines and pre-shrines were sometimes served by ritualists visiting from a larger nearby shrine.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: As ritualists were public officials, only men were allowed to serve as one. Post-war, both genders can serve as such.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Notes: Most ritualists are ethnic-Japanese, but there are cases both pre and post-war of non-ethnic-Japanese becoming ritualists, such as Koreans in colonial Korea and Westerners post-war.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: It was common for ritualists to rotate at larger shrines, the same as other public servants. At smaller shrines, local ritualists often served for life, but this was not mandated.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Shinen-kai, Hosai-kai and other support organizations helped maintain and fundraise for the shrine.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: Prewar shrines were a part of the government bureaucracy. Postwar, shrines conduct their own finances through a board of members (sodai).

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

Notes: Gifts of land formed a source of income for some shrines, but overseas shrines primarily relied upon donations/taxes for income.

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

Notes: Unlike in the home islands, overseas shrines rarely possessed extra land to lease out.

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: During the war, ration collection points were sometimes located at shrines.

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Notes: But there are shrines built at water management facilities, such as Maruyama Mizu Jinja in Taihoku/Taipei, which was built to commemorate workers who died in an accident during construction of the modern water works.

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: Railways frequently built train stations in front of larger shrines.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Public Park

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Notes: Shrines might produce a shrine history or other records, but it is not especially stored at the shrine.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: Although the Japanese classics have often considered "Shinto scriptures", they are not associated with any overseas shrines.

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: specify: It depends on the size of the shrine. An example of a larger shrine is Taiwan Jinja, which had 65 thousand people visit during its main festival in 1901., Taiwan Jinja Shamosho Hensan, ed.. Taiwan Jinja Shi. Edited by Taiwan Jinja Shamosho Hensan. Taipei: Taiwan Nichinichi Shinpousha, 1916.